

**THE RULE OF LAW AS A UNIVERSAL PRINCIPLE OF ENSURING
HUMAN RIGHTS**

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Abstract This article is devoted to the issues of the rule of law, the history of its origin as a concept and legal phenomenon. The rule of law is positioned as a universal principle of ensuring human rights, which all states are obliged to adhere to. The article analyzes the legal nature and content of the rule of law as a principle, a legal phenomenon, and a conceptual approach to modern human rights. Foreign experience in implementing the rule of law in the CIS countries, the European Council, and the United States is examined. The role of international organizations in ensuring the rule of law is studied and defined. As a result of the analysis, it is revealed that the simple formation of a perfect system of legislation that enshrines basic human rights and freedoms and establishes an effective legislative procedure is not enough to build a democratic society. The principle of the rule of law is, in fact, the only effective means of ensuring the inviolability of democracy, as well as one of its main features, and its maintenance and control is a guarantee of ensuring human rights to the extent that decent living conditions are created for everyone. The article also analyzes the value of the Rule of Law index. The World Justice Project (WJP) is discussed using the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: the rule of law, constitutional rights, the rule of law index, restriction of powers of government institutions, absence of corruption, order and security, protection of fundamental rights, transparency of government institutions, compliance with laws, civil justice, criminal justice.

The rule of law is a universal principle for ensuring human rights. In his report *In Larger Freedom: Towards Development, Security and Human Rights for All* (A/59/2005), the Secretary-General noted that “it is necessary to get rid of want and fear, but this is not enough. All human beings have the right to be treated with dignity and respect” (paragraph 27). “The key to providing people with such decent treatment and respect is the full implementation of human rights, and their protection is the rule of human rights” [1].

A legal democratic state is a state in which the rule of law is implemented.

The lack of certainty in the content of the category of the rule of law is largely due to the debatability and lack of unambiguous answers to key questions that can give an idea of this phenomenon. What is the legal basis and content of the rule of law? What is meant by law in the case under consideration, and over the acts of what types and levels of regulation does it have supremacy? What is meant by the rule of law, and what are its mechanisms? Is it expedient to single out and evaluate the rule of law as an independent legal phenomenon for the development of legal doctrine and practice?

It is known that the doctrine of the rule of law as a certain system of views on the structure and development of legal reality has been formed over several centuries, while historically its "homeland" is considered to be the system of common Anglo-Saxon law, where its content was first defined, which subsequently allowed the rule of law to be approved as fundamental constitutional principle of English law. Traditionally, the work of the English scientist A.V. Dicey on the foundations of public law in England. He conceptually substantiated the meaning and essence of the rule of law, including highlighting such components of this phenomenon as preventing the administration from abusing its power, subordinating all subjects of the country

to English laws and courts, and judicial protection of human rights and freedoms.

Modern theorists of English constitutional law have enriched their ideas about the rule of law, focusing on the limitation of public power with the help of law, on determining the boundness of the activities of courts only by law, and not by law, and on the special significance of the judiciary in protecting human rights and freedoms. At the same time, important attention is paid to the relationship of the rule of law with the generally recognized principles of international law and fundamental human rights guaranteed by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 and the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950.

The rule of law is a universal principle. The need for universal provision and observance of the rule of law, both at the national and international levels, was recognized by all UN member states in 2005 in the Outcome Document of the World Summit (§ 134) [2]. As stated in the Preamble and Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) [3], the rule of law is one of the core values shared by the European Union and its members [4]. In its 2014 paper *New Principles for Strengthening the Rule of Law*, the European Commission recalls that “the rule of law is steadily becoming the dominant organizational model of modern constitutional law and international organizations governing the exercise of state power.” An increasing number of states in their national constitutions refer to the principle of the rule of law [5].

The UN has proclaimed the rule of law as a universal basic principle, for example in the Rule of Law Indicators. At the regional level, this has been done by the Organization of American States, in particular in the Constitutive Act of the Inter-American Democratic Charter of the African Union. References to the rule of law can also be found in various Arab League documents. The rule of law is mentioned in the preamble of the Statute of the Council of Europe as one of the three “principles that form the basis of true democracy”, along with

individual freedom and political freedoms. Article 3 of the Charter states that a prerequisite for the admission of a new State to membership in the Organization is respect for the rule of law. Thus, the rule of law, along with democracy and human rights, is one of the three intertwined and overlapping core principles of the Council of Europe. The close relationship between the rule of law and a democratic society is emphasized in various formulations of the European Court of Human Rights, for example: “a democratic society that recognizes the rule of law”, “a democratic society based on the rule of law” and more generally “the rule of law in a democratic society”. Ensuring these three principles - respect for human rights, pluralistic democracy and the rule of law - is considered the single and main goal of the Council of Europe.

The rule of law is systematically mentioned in the main political documents of the Council of Europe, as well as in various conventions and recommendations. It is mentioned in particular as an element of common heritage in the preamble of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR). The rule of law is named as a basic principle of European democracies in Resolution Res (2002) 12 establishing the European Commission for the Efficiency of the Administration of Justice (CEPEJ) and is referred to as a priority in the Statute of the Venice Commission. At the same time, none of the documents of the Council of Europe defines the rule of law. The Council of Europe has also not created any specific oversight mechanisms for rule of law issues.

Despite this, on a number of occasions the Council of Europe has taken action to promote and strengthen the rule of law through its institutions, notably the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), the European Commission for the Efficiency of the Administration of Justice (CEPEJ), the Advisory Council of European Judges (CCJE), the Group of States against Corruption (GRECO), the Monitoring Committee of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, the Commissioner for Human Rights and the Venice Commission. In its

2011 rule of law report, the Venice Commission considered the principle of the rule of law in the light of Resolution 1594 (2007) of the Parliamentary Assembly, which pointed out the need to ensure the correct interpretation of the terms "rule of law", "Rechtsstaat" and "Etat de droit" or "prééminence du droit" in the spirit of the principle of legality and due process [5].

At its 86th plenary meeting (March 2011), the Venice Commission approved the Rule of Law Report (CDLAD (2011) 003rev). In this report, the main elements of the rule of law (Rule of Law), Rechtsstaat and Etat de droit were identified. Attached to the report was a first draft of a checklist of questions to assess the rule of law in a given State. According to natural law theory, the rule of law requires that all normative legal acts and all activities of state power serve to protect dignity, freedom and human rights [6].

The Venice Commission analyzed definitions proposed by various authors representing different systems of law and public organization, as well as different legal cultures. The Commission concluded that the concept of the rule of law implies a clear and predictable legal system in which every citizen is entitled to decent, equal and reasonable treatment in accordance with the law by all persons in power, and also has the opportunity to challenge their decisions in independent and impartial courts within the framework of a fair trial. The Commission warned against a purely formal approach to the concept of the rule of law, requiring only that the actions of an official be authorized by law. "Rule by force of law" or "Rule by law" or even "Justice by law" are all distortions of the concept of the rule of law [7].

The concept of the rule of law implies that rules must be published, stable and predictable in their application. An important requirement is the accessibility of the justice system and its independence from the executive and legislative branches of government. Viewed rationally, the rule of law does not provide an assessment of the fairness of the rules themselves, but rather establishes the procedural attributes that a legal system should have. Today, the

rule of law is a global goal of the international community, the achievement of which is possible only through international integration, due to globalization and technological progress, which contribute to the growth of interaction between states at the international and regional levels.

The World Justice Project (WJP), an international independent non-profit organization, published for the first time the Rule of Law Index 2010. The organization promotes the rule of law, the principle that recognizes the primacy of law over the state and holds all its individuals and institutions accountable.

The Rule of Law Index® World Justice Project is the world's leading source of original, independent rule of law data. Covering 128 countries and jurisdictions, the index relies on national surveys of more than 130,000 households and 4,000 legal practitioners and experts to measure how the rule of law is perceived and implemented around the world [8].

Uzbekistan in 2019 ranked 94th out of 126 participants and 12th out of 13 participants in the region of Eastern Europe and Central Asia [9]. The compilers of the index note that the situation with the rule of law in the country has improved, which allowed it to rise by 2 positions in the world ranking.

In the region, the place of Uzbekistan has not changed. The overall score of Uzbekistan is 0.46. In 2020, Uzbekistan rose to 92nd place out of 128 states [10], which is a good indicator, since the country has risen 2 levels higher over the year. WJP rates countries on several factors, including lack of corruption, order and security, fundamental rights, civil justice, and more. We have the lowest indicators in terms of government transparency and the absence of corruption, and the highest indicator is order and security, according to this criterion, we are in 11th place in the world [11].

In general, it can be stated that the legal positions of the highest judicial bodies, especially constitutional courts, are becoming the most important tool for ensuring the doctrine of the rule of law and the implementation of legal life.

At the same time, there is also a feedback - the influence of the rule of law on the judiciary as the most important doctrinal and legal tool for the development of judicial discretion and activism, the unification of national judicial and legal practices and the establishment of suprapositive general legal values in them.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the doctrine of the rule of law adopted by legal practice undoubtedly opens up additional prospects and opportunities for the implementation of international law, the development of the national legal system in the context of ensuring human rights and freedoms and sovereignty of the individual, optimizing the activities of public authorities and the limits of their permissible impact on public relations, strengthening the independence of the judiciary.

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